

reSEARCH-EU

Data Management Plan

D.1.2

2nd version

WP 1 –Task 1.3 Led by UNIST

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017494

reSEARCH-EU

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**REINFORCING
SUSTAINABLE
ACTIONS,
RESILIENCE,
COOPERATION
AND
HARMONISATION
ACROSS AND BY
THE SEA-EU
ALLIANCE**

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Deliverable identification

Deliverable No. and Title	D1.2. Data Management Plan
Leader	Prof. Mile Dželalija (University of Split)
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<p><u>Abstract</u></p> <p>The Data Management Plan is a document that provides an overview on the policies implemented in the reSEArch-EU Project regarding collection, storing, sharing and publication of research data through the life of the project. This document has been created taking the <i>Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020</i> as its main reference.</p>	

Versions and contribution history

Version	Date	Modified by	Reason
0	02/06/2021	N/A	Version sent for review to the QandES and the Extended EC.
1	17/06/2021	Juan Ramón Real (UCA)	First version, produced after the review and approval of the QandES and the Extended EC.
2	20/04/2022	Juan Ramón Real (UCA)	Second version after the review of the DMP by the Open Research Data Officers of all SEA-EU partners at the Open Science Staff Week (January 2022) and the completion of the first research-related deliverables of the project.

Changes incorporated to the second version (April 2022)

- Updated data summary: all research data produced in the project is sort by WP; the data categories match those existing on Zenodo; explicit provisions in reference to the data formats to be employed have been added.
- Making data findable. The naming convention for datasets uploaded to the repository has been improved; an explicit mention to the DublinCore metadata scheme has been incorporated.
- Making data accessible. This section, though incorporates the same content, has been reformulated to make it gain more clarity.
- Making data inter-operable. The preference of open-source formats over proprietary formats has been made explicit.
- Making data re-usable. The adoption of CC-NA licenses has been added as the preferred option.
- Distribution of roles. The DMO will send the datasets to the DMC and the latter will be in charge of uploading them to the repository.
- Data security and ethical aspects. A copy of every dataset uploaded to the repository will be stored on Alfresco as a backup.

List of acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
CAU	University of Kiel (Germany)
CFREU	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
DMC	Data Management Coordinator
DMO	Data Management Operator
DMP	Data Management Plan
Extended EC	Extended Executive Committee
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
QandES	Quality and Ethics Subcommittee
UBO	University of Western Brittany (France)
UCA	University of Cadiz (Spain)
UG	University of Gdansk (Poland)
UM	University of Malta
UNIST	University of Split (Croatia)
WP	Work Package

The reSEArch-EU Project

reSEArch-EU (reinforcing Sustainable Actions, resilience, cooperation and harmonisation across and by the SEA-EU Alliance) is a research project funded under the SwafS Call *Support for the Research and Innovation dimension of European Universities*.

This project has been granted to the European University of the Seas (SEA-EU), a consortium made up of six European coastal universities with the common purpose of building an European campus with joint educational programmes as well as a shared research infrastructure able to multiply the innovative potential of this Alliance. SEA-EU was originated initially as an Erasmus+ Project in 2019, though in 2020 the European Commission, via its Research Executive Agency, launched this SwafS call to provide the European Universities with additional support to build a shared research infrastructure and develop a common research agenda.

The Data Management Plan (henceforth, DMP) gives a thorough explanation on how both research data and research results originated in this project are to be collected, stored, shared and made available. The DMP addresses three different needs at once:

- It provides guidance to the project partners on open research management within the scope of this project.
- It serves the European Commission services as an assessment tool to monitor how research data is being collected and made public in reSEArch-EU.
- It may be in the future a reference in research data management for European projects, especially for upcoming European Universities in need of guidance into how to manage research data originated in joint projects.

The Data Management Plan, located under WP1 (led by UCA) is included within Task 1.3 (led by UNIST). Therefore, close collaboration between both partners has been essential in the creation of this document. In addition to that, since all project partners will have to deal with research data management, they have been consulted before the approval and submission of the Data Management Plan, which took place in June 2021. They will be informed and consulted before any further updates or modifications made on this document.

1. Data summary

Work Package 2. Increasing resilience and anti-fragility of research and innovation					
Type of data	Task	Description	Collection	Purpose	File format
Questionnaires	2.1.	Survey based on the antifragility analytical framework	Primary data	To measure the perceptions held by members of the SEA-EU Antifragility Think Tank with regards to the antifragility of their respective universities.	XML
	2.3.	Survey of research fields, groups and situations where remote work is already practised	Primary data	To explore existing remote work practises in research and innovation with the goal to produce a case study analysis	PDF
	2.5	Survey on every partner university's past experience measuring their carbon footprint emissions	Primary data	To gather information on previous initiatives measuring the carbon footprint at the different SEA-EU universities	XML
Media (e.g., video, audio, image)	2.1	[video] Recordings of the meetings of the Anti-Fragility Think Tank	Primary data	To analyse and discuss with experts from different research fields the current challenges for today's universities	MP4
	2.3	[video] Recording of the workshop on remote work in research and innovation	Primary data	To review the answers provided to the survey on remotization of research infrastructure and to build up a case study based on them	MP4

Documents (e.g., reports, manuals, presentations, policy papers)	2.1.	AFTT rules of procedure and key areas of impact.	N.A.	To state the rules of the procedure and identification of anti-fragility sources and key areas of impact in universities will be set to guide the alliance in times of unforeseen events.	PDF
	2.2.	Digital transformation of research and innovation roadmap.	N.A.	Roadmap for digital transformation will be developed according to identified shared goals, actions, experiences and barriers, aimed at exploiting the opportunities and building resilience of the alliance.	PDF
	2.3.	Case study: Remote work and remotization of infrastructure case study.	N.A.	A case study on remote work and remotization as tools towards achieving Alliance anti-fragility.	PDF
	2.4.	Guiding Principles for the SEA-EU Academy	N.A.	SEA-EU Academy will be constituted as a virtual teaching space for the capacity building of the alliance	PDF
	2.5	SEA-EU position paper on the footprint of R&I activities	Results of the survey on experiences measuring carbon footprint	Paper presenting context of the action and methodology on how to consider the 'ecological footprint of professional activities in R&I	PDF

Work Package 3. Bridging the gap with the innovation ecosystem					
Type of data	Task	Description	Collection	Purpose	File format
Questionnaires	3.1.	Survey on innovation and entrepreneurial potential of Alliance with HEInnovate.	Primary data	To form the basis of a public Report (deliverable D3.1.)	XML
	3.2	Patent Landscape Tool Development (creation of a joint database of patents and patent applications of SEA-EU Alliance members)	Spreadsheets sent by all partners	To identify inventors' networks and scientific trends in industries and between countries.	XML
	3.5	Preparatory survey on entrepreneurial skills for the Spin-Off Competence Lab	Primary data	To have an overview on the current training needs of SEA-EU's research community in terms of turning research projects into business ideas, so that the learning modules of the Spin-Off Competence Lab meet their needs.	XML
Media (e.g., video, audio, image)	3.3	[video] Recordings of the workshops organized on technology transfer and IPR management	N.A.	The recordings of the workshops on intellectual property rights management will be made publicly available to allow any viewer to learn about such topics.	MP4

Documents (e.g., reports, manuals, presentations, policy papers)	3.1.	Summary report on Innovative and Entrepreneurial potential of the SEA-EU.	Results of the survey on entrepreneurial potential of the Alliance	To help design solutions tailored to the Alliance's needs for a strategic approach to innovation and entrepreneurship.	PDF
	3.2	Patent Landscape Report	Data retrieved from the Patent Landscape Tool (joint patent database) as well the purchased reports on patent clusters.	To support the development of a research unit's intellectual property strategy and to identify emerging technologies and technology trends in the industry.	PDF

Work Package 4. Co-designing, co-creating and co-delivering for knowledge democratisation					
Type of data	Task	Description	Collection	Purpose	File format
Questionnaires	4.1	Online questionnaire collecting information about universities' experience with involving non-academic stakeholders.	Primary data from participants; publicly available sources (websites, publications)	The information is analysed and will be used for a final report (to be published online in Dec 2021)	XML
Documents (e.g., reports, manuals, presentations, policy papers)	4.1	Information case studies (running or finished projects) collected during the preparation of the report on stakeholder engagement approaches. A template will be used to collect the information from all partner.	Templates filled by participants.	To provide information which will contribute to the completion of the report on stakeholder engagement approaches.	PDF
	4.1	Report on stakeholder engagement approaches across the SEA-EU Alliance.	N.A.	To document existing practices and approaches to stakeholder engagement across the SEA-EU Alliance, taking as starting point previous experiences in projects involving citizen science or co-creation activities at some degree.	PDF

	4.3	Good practice guide for transdisciplinarity and stakeholder engagement	N.A.	Compilation of both previous and newly adopted practices and approaches in stakeholder engagement, taking into consideration the lessons learned after the completion of the pilot activities in trans disciplinarity and stakeholder engagement.	PDF
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Work Package 5. Building an Open Future: Fostering open science across the SEA-EU community and beyond					
Type of data	Task	Description	Collection	Purpose	File format
Questionnaires	5.1	Survey of best practices in Open Science	Primary data	To identify the 'state of play' of Open Science practices at each SEA-EU university.	XML
Documents (e.g., reports, manuals, presentations, policy papers)	5.1	Report on current practices in Open Science	N.A.	To compile current procedures, methodologies and resources devoted to research data management in every partner university.	PDF
	5.2	SEA-EU Open Research Data Management Policy	N.A.	To develop and set up a framework for research data management across all SEA-EU partners, considering the existing policies and regulations at the European, national and institutional level.	PDF
	5.2	SEA-EU Open Research Data Toolkit	N.A.	To provide guidelines for the implementation of joint research data policies.	PDF
	5.4	Plan Open Science Ambassadors programme - Training Documents	N.A.	To support the OSA's endeavour in promoting open science practices across their universities' research communities.	PDF, MP4
	5.5	Training Workshops documents/presentations	N.A.	To support both OSAs and ORDOs in the implementation of the ORD system and policies developed at the Consortium level, as well as to provide them guidance into how to involve the whole academic community in consolidating open science practices.	PDF, MP4

Work Package 6. Designing and developing a SEA-EU long-term Research Plan					
Type of data	Task	Description	Collection	Purpose	File format
Questionnaires	6.1	Survey on these defended in every SEA-EU partner during five years before the beginning of this task (2017-2021)	Data from each partner's databases	To acquire an overview into the main areas of interest of emerging scientists across the SEA-EU Alliance.	XML
	6.1	Survey on the scientific conferences held in every partner university in the last five years before the beginning of this task (2017-2021)	Data from each partner's database	To get an overview of the main areas of interest for researchers delivering conferences in every university.	XML
	6.2	Survey on the main challenges for the SEA-EU research community	Primary data	To collect principal investigators' opinions on the main research challenges.	XML
Documents (e.g., reports, manuals, presentations, policy papers)	6.2	Digest Paper on the main challenges for the SEA-EU research community	N.A.	To compile nowadays' global challenges and insights into how academia, and especially the SEA-EU Alliance, could contribute to face them.	PDF

2. FAIR Data

2.1. Making data findable

To ensure that all data generated and made available in reSEArch-EU is easily findable, project partners will have three tools at their disposal: identifiers, metadata, and naming conventions.

Tool	Description of use
Identifiers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: a persistent identifier will be assigned to every report/deliverable uploaded to the repository. Handle: this identifier will be attributed to every dataset uploaded to the repository.
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All datasets will comply with the requirements of the Dublin Core metadata schema.
Naming conventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All datasets uploaded to the repositories will follow this naming scheme: project-name_date[year-month-day]_title_v[number]_deliverable-number.fileformat This will facilitate identification, time allocation and clarity to differentiate diverse versions of the same document that might have been created over time.

2.2. Making data accessible

The completion of a common policy on open research data management, as well as the establishment of a system to interconnect all partners' institutional repositories -thus consolidating a joint open research data system- are specific objectives of reSEArch-EU that will have significant, long-lasting effects on how research is conducted across the SEA-EU Alliance.

Whereas the definitive completion of such tasks is expected by the end of 2023, the SEA-EU partners need to implement a quicker, simpler solution to provide themselves with a common platform so that all research data produced in reSEArch-EU can be stored in the same place. To meet such an objective, all datasets created in reSEArch-EU will be uploaded to **Zenodo**, an open repository created by the CERN and supported by OpenAIRE. A **collection for reSEArch-EU** has been created and it will host all research data produced through its lifespan.

2.3. Making data inter-operable

The diverse nature of research matters covered in reSEArch-EU makes necessary to adopt a flexible approach with regards to data and methodologies, and discussions will be held between participants in the different WPs and the Data Management Coordinators to agree on diverse solutions. In any case, **open-source formats** will be preferred over proprietary formats in the dataset files uploaded to Zenodo.

2.4. Making data re-usable

As a publicly funded project committed to improve inter-university integration in research and technology transfer, the project partners will adopt a **Creative Commons Non-Attribution (CC NA) license** as a priority criterion for both research data and research results made publicly available.

3. Allocation of resources

3.1. Costs

Since reSEArch-EU will make use of an open-source, freely available tool such as Zenodo as repository, the implementation of this Data Management will not suppose additional costs to those already planned in the project proposal.

3.2. Distribution of roles across the consortium

A two-dimension scheme for the allocation of responsibilities with regards to data management in reSEArch-EU has been established. Two main roles will be established:

The Data Management Coordinator (DMC). Leading WP1 and Task 1.3 respectively, both UCA and UNIST will assume this role, whose main responsibilities are:

- Submission of the DMP to the European Commission.
- Communications with the European Commission in all matters related to data management.
- Guidance and assistance to other partners in the implementation of this DMP.
- Ensuring general compliance with the terms established in this DMP for data management.
- Upload of both research data and results to the selected repository.

The Data Management Operators (DMO). Since all partners will be involved in data management as part of their respective research activities, all of them will have the status of DMO, which imply the following responsibilities:

- Collection of data in their respective research activities, in compliance with the procedures established in this Data Management Plan.
- Submission of both research data and results to the DMCs so that they can upload them to the selected repository.
- Suggestions of review and updates of the DMP.

The formal nominee for each of these roles, and hence the person with the responsibility to meet their requirements, will be every Work Package leader. It is strongly suggested to ask for the support of the SEA-EU Open Research Data Officer appointed at their university in carrying out this task.

4. Data security and ethical aspects

The allocation of the datasets on a widely trusted, well known public repository as **Zenodo** where data security and integrity is highly guaranteed. To reassure data recovery in case of any disruptions in the Zenodo repository, a **backup** of all datasets uploaded will be stored on a dedicated site within the Alfresco platform used for internal document sharing in the SEA-EU Alliance.

Every dataset, as well as every research result, to be uploaded to Zenodo will previously undergo a two-step curation process (firstly by the DMO and then by the DMC) that will ensure that all data is properly anonymized before its upload to the public repository. More information on personal data protection policies adopted in reSEArch-EU can be found in the ethics self-assessment produced in June 2021.